

Maternal & Child Health Policy Crisis in the U.S.- Systematic Literature Review

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***Abstract*—Despite global progress in reducing maternal mortality, the United States (U.S.) continues to face alarmingly poor maternal and child health (MCH) outcomes, ranking last among high-income countries. This systematic literature review examines the structural drivers behind these outcomes, including systemic racism, historical inequities, and the persistent neglect of key health determinants. Utilizing a root cause analysis (RCA) framework, the paper dissects the MCH crisis across distal, intermediate, and proximal levels to uncover the interconnected factors contributing to preventable maternal deaths, particularly amongst marginalized populations. By exploring barriers embedded in healthcare access, governance structures, and socioeconomic systems, the review demonstrates that the MCH crisis in the U.S. reflects broad institutional failures. The paper concludes by identifying actionable strategies for improvement and introduces a forthcoming honors thesis that will investigate how political leadership and regional characteristics influence maternal health outcomes across the U.S.**

***Keywords* - maternal and child health (MCH), crisis, structural drivers**

I. INTRODUCTION

The United States is facing a MCH crisis despite its economic advancement. While being one of the wealthiest nations in the world, and spending more on healthcare than any other high-income country, the U.S. continues to report some of the worst maternal health outcomes among its peers [1]. In fact, it ranks last among high-income nations in maternal mortality [2], with disproportionately high rates of pregnancy-related deaths, complications and illnesses, particularly amongst marginalized populations [3]. These outcomes are not random, but rather by the result of historical systemic injustices such as institutional racism, economic inequality, and the political and commercial determinant factors that shape health access and outcomes [4].

This paper presents a systematic literature review of the U.S. MCH crisis, using a RCA framework to explore the complex interchange of factors contributing to worsening MCH outcomes. It situates the U.S. within a global and comparative health systems context, drawing attention to how determinants of health interact across distal, intermediate, and proximal levels to shape maternal health disparities. The review highlights how historical inequities in U.S. health policy and practice affect the nation's current MCH outcomes.

In addition to identifying the determinant drivers of poor MCH outcomes, this paper examines how state-level public policy differences and regional disparities influence access to obstetric services and health equity. Drawing on a broad range of academic sources, national data, and global health comparisons, the review uncovers how systemic neglect and policy misalignment have perpetuated maternal mortality and morbidity across generations in the U.S., particularly among communities of color and low-income populations.

The paper concludes by outlining future directions for research and policy change, including a forthcoming honors thesis that will build upon this analysis to investigate how political leadership and geographic context impact maternal outcomes across the U.S. By comparing states with different political affiliations and public health infrastructures, the next phase of study seeks to provide evidence-based insight into how structural reform can improve maternal and child health outcomes nationwide.

II. THE GLOBAL BURDEN OF MCH OUTCOMES

Despite a global 40% decline in the maternal mortality rates (MMR) between 2000 and 2023, maternal mortality remains alarmingly high. In 2023, over 700 women around the globe died daily from preventable causes related to pregnancy and childbirth, or approximately one woman every two minutes. The vast majority (92%) of these deaths were preventable and occurred in low and lower-middle-income

countries, amounting to an estimated 260,000 maternal deaths [5].

The situation in the United States is particularly concerning. According to the *Mirror, Mirror 2024* report, the U.S. ranks last among ten high-income nations in overall health system performance and health outcomes. A health outcome measure looked at by the report was mortality caused by health care, which are deaths considered preventable and treatable through timely and effective health care [1]. In the U.S., eight out of ten (84%) pregnancy-related deaths are preventable [6].

While comparable OECD countries like the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, and Germany excel in access, affordability, and availability of care, the U.S. continues to struggle despite spending the most on healthcare relative to gross domestic product (GDP). More than 16% of the United States's GDP, or over four trillion dollars, was spent on health care in 2022 [1]. The top-performing systems of Australia, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom demonstrate that better MCH outcomes are achievable with efficient and equitable government policy frameworks, not exclusively money [1]. Australia spent an estimated \$252.5 billion dollars on health goods and services in 2022 [7], the Netherlands spent 113.5 billion euros on health care in 2024 (10% of country's GDP) [8], the United Kingdom's healthcare expenditure was around 292 billion euros in 2023 (10.9% of country's GDP) [9], and France, the country who spends the second most on healthcare relative to GDP according to the *Mirror, Mirror 2024* report, spent only 314 billion euros on health expenditures in 2022 (11.9%) [10].

With these noted deficiencies and systemic disparities, this paper systematically examines the policy failures contributing to the MCH crisis in the United States, situating them within both global and comparative health system contexts.

III. MCH OUTCOMES IN U.S.: EVIDENCE FOR A CRISIS?

Maternal health crisis is defined as a worsening pattern of preventable deaths and complications related to pregnancy along the peripartum period [11]. As the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine *Birth Settings in America* report highlighted, "The current U.S. maternity care system is fraught with inequities in access and quality and high costs, and there is growing recognition of the mismatch between the collective expectations of the care and support women deserve and what they actually receive" [12]. People giving birth in the U.S. are more likely to face mistreatment, experience serious complications, or even death than people in any other high-income country. Moreover, people living in the U.S. today are 50% more likely to die during childbirth than their own mothers [12]. The risks are even greater for Black or Indigenous people, even though many of these issues are preventable. Failures in communication and teamwork among clinical teams play a role in 80 – 90% of cases of patient harm,

and recent data show that more than eight out of ten (84%) pregnancy-related deaths are preventable [6], [13].

The maternal health crisis in the U.S. is influenced by systemic racism and the effects of historical economic and social systems of oppression [4]. Today, these systems continue to endanger the lives of Black Americans and other communities of color, prompting many U.S. cities to declare racism a public health emergency [14]. Decades of disinvestment, discriminatory zoning, and reliance on local and state revenue generation for public services have exacerbated community-level inequities based on skin color, such as rates for chronic disease, housing instability, and over-policing [14]. All of these inequities increase maternal health risk by increasing exposure to chronic stress factors, such as limiting access to quality care, good schools, safe housing, green spaces, jobs, healthy food, and transportation [14].

The social determinants of health, such as socioeconomic status, income, education level, race, geographic location, and others are all closely tied to maternal outcomes. Women living in high-poverty areas face more than twice the maternal mortality rate of those in wealthier communities. Similarly, being unmarried, U.S.-born, having lower educational attainment, or residing in rural areas is associated with a 50–114% increase in maternal mortality risk [15].

Further compounding this crisis is the state of healthcare infrastructure. More than 35% of U.S. counties are considered maternity care deserts, leaving over 2.3 million women with limited or no access to maternal services [16]. The MMR in the U.S. remains far higher than similarly economically developed countries. In 2022, there were approximately 22 maternal deaths per 100,000 live births [2], compared to 4.8 per 100,000 in Australia [17], 7 in France [18], and 12 in Canada [19]. Disparities across racial groups are distinct in the U.S., with maternal mortality being the lowest amongst Asian American women (13.2 per 100,000) and highest among Black women (49.5 per 100,000) [2].

In addition to mortality, severe maternal morbidity, which are severe health conditions caused by pregnancy throughout the peripartum period such as heart attacks, heart failure, eclampsia, blood infection, and hysterectomy [3], affect approximately 60,000 women annually in the United States. These unexpected and often avoidable complications during labor and delivery often have long-term health consequences [20]. The Nulliparous, Term, Singleton, Vertex (NTSV) C-section rates remain high at 25.3%, while episiotomy rates have dropped to 3.4%, giving the U.S. an improvement in obstetric practices [21].

Broader reproductive health indicators also reflect underlying systemic challenges. In 2023, teen births accounted for 3.9% of all U.S. births, with approximately 141,000 births being from teenagers aged 15 to 19 [22]. Across the general

population, the infant mortality rate in 2022 was 5.6 deaths per 1,000 live births [23], and the fetal mortality rate was 5.53 fetal deaths at 20 weeks of gestation or more per 1,000 live births and fetal deaths, figures that remain significantly higher than in other developed nations [24].

Structural barriers across the peripartum period further restrict the delivery of timely and adequate care for low-income and rural populations. Care deserts are a prominent issue, roughly 1 in 10 U.S. residents lack health insurance [25], and 7.3% of adults report being unable to obtain needed medical care due to cost [26].

Together, these disparities in maternal health outcomes bring to the light the systemic policy failures, such as underfunded public health infrastructure, institutional racism, and barriers to healthcare access that disproportionately harm marginalized populations in the United States [14].

IV. EXPLORING MCH OUTCOMES FROM A ROOT CAUSE ANALYSIS PERSPECTIVE

Health Disparities are Driven by Social and Economic Inequities

Fig. 1 [27]

A root cause analysis (RCA) tries to describe a wide range of approaches, tools, and techniques used to uncover causes of problems [28]. MCH outcomes are shaped by a complex interplay of factors that operate at distal, intermediate, and proximal levels. At the distal level, structural forces such as historical injustices, systemic racism, cultural biases, and discriminatory policies lay the foundation for present-day inequities. Distal forces directly shape the intermediate level, such as access to quality education, healthcare, food, and environment. Distal and intermediate forces explain the surface level factors most closely linked to health outcomes, such as

socioeconomic status, life at home, and food stability among others. This is also known as proximal level [27].

For example, in the Black community, slavery, Jim Crow laws, the GI Bill, redlining, and mass incarceration are all historically injustice systems that continue to influence the disparities in health outcomes (distal). The Black community being subjected to redlining decades ago makes them more likely today to have under-resourced schools, attain a lower socioeconomic status, and have fewer healthcare facilities (intermediate). Having a lower socioeconomic status often leads to unstable housing, limited access to healthy food, and poorer living conditions, and these factors increase chronic stress and the risk of illness over time. Using this RCA model helps us to understand how it is essential to address maternal health disparities at the root, rather than focusing solely on surface level symptoms. We must identify and strengthen upstream determinants and factors as they pertain to MCH outcomes versus triaging downstream health issues.

V. THE INFLUENCE OF COMMERCIAL, POLITICAL & SOCIAL DETERMINANTS OF HEALTH

Maternal and child health outcomes in the United States are shaped not only by individual lifestyle choices, but by the structural determinants that can impact human potential, such as policies and social systems [29]. Understanding how the political, commercial, and social determinants of health are essential to addressing the root causes of persistent inequities in maternal well-being is a primary focus of this review.

Political Determinants of Health (PDOHs)

At the highest level, political determinants of health (PDOHs) shape the distribution of power and resources that influence all other determinants and public health outcomes. These include the laws, policies, and governance systems that set the conditions for health access, equity, and outcomes [30]. In the context of maternal and child health, political determinants directly affect access to prenatal, perinatal, and postpartum care through mechanisms such as Medicaid expansion [30], Affordable Care Act (ACA) adoption [31], and state-level reproductive health policies. Additionally, laws governing paid time off, environmental protections, and educational attainment equity play a significant role in shaping maternal health across the life course [32]. Policy choices made by those in power can either protect or harm maternal and child health, particularly for marginalized communities.

For example, in 2024, Elon Musk launched “Colossus,” an AI supercomputing facility in a low-income, predominantly Black neighborhood in Memphis. Although permitted to run 15 methane-powered turbines, the facility operates 33, drastically increasing local pollution and pollution-related illness, threatening local MCH. Weak regulatory enforcement and permissive zoning policies fueled by systemic

racism allow projects like this to operate specifically in marginalized communities who have historically had less political power and the fewest protections [33].

Commercial Determinants of Health (CDoHs)

Deeply connected and intertwined to the political environment are the commercial determinants of health (CDoHs), which refer to the conditions, actions and omissions by commercial actors that affect health [34]. Corporations shape maternal and child health through marketing, political lobbying, and controlling the cost of goods and services. For instance, aggressive marketing of infant formula, sale of ultra-processed foods and sugary beverages, and targeted advertising of tobacco, alcohol, and vaping products contribute to increased risks of obesity, chronic disease, and adverse birth outcomes, especially for marginalized populations [34]. Furthermore, misinformation spread by commercial actors on maternal health and their products, often spread on their social media platforms, distorts public understanding and undermines informed decision-making, particularly in the younger generation [34].

Thus, without appropriate regulation by the political environment, the interests of corporations often take precedence over maternal and child health outcomes, potentially undermining the overall health of the local communities.

Social Determinants of Health (SDoHs)

Sequentially following the political and commercial influences of health lie the social determinants of health (SDoHs), or the everyday conditions in which one's health such as economic status, religion, social and community context, gender, sexuality are affected. These non-medical, but social and environmental contextual factors profoundly shape maternal and child health and well-being. The key social determinants critical to maternal and child health according to *Fostering Livable Communities for Birthing People* [14] are:

1. Healthy and Attainable Housing
2. Reliable and Affordable Transit Systems
3. Safe Water, Air, and Open Spaces
4. Nourishing Food Systems
5. Equitable Education and Jobs
6. Person-Centered and Dignified Healthcare
7. Connected and Cohesive Communities
8. Anti-racist Neighborhood Security

Research further shows that women living in high-poverty communities face more than double the maternal mortality rate of those in more affluent areas, and that factors such as lower educational attainment, unmarried status, rural residence, and U.S.-born status are associated with 50–114% higher risks of maternal mortality [15]. These outcomes are not random but are a result of political and commercial decisions.

Access to quality housing, food, and healthcare is a combined neglect of public policy and uneven commercial investment, and in 2022, 35% of U.S. counties were classified as maternity care deserts, affecting more than 2.3 million women [16]. Political determinants set the rules, commercial determinants exploit those rules, and social determinants are the lived experiences of people affected by them both with relevant health outcomes.

VI. OTHER FACTORS AFFECTING MCH OUTCOMES

To further demonstrate the ongoing maternal and child health crisis in the United States, we will explore the striking racial, ethnic, and socioeconomic disparities in health coverage, chronic illness, and poverty that are deeply interwoven into the ongoing maternal and child health crisis.

Health coverage remains deeply unequal across racial and ethnic groups. As of the most recent data, American Indian and Alaska Native (AIAN) individuals under the age of 65 had the highest uninsured rate at 18.7%, followed closely by Hispanic individuals at 17.9%. Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander (NHPI) (12.8%) and Black individuals (9.7%) also experienced significantly higher rates of being uninsured than their White counterparts (6.5%) [35]. Lack of insurance often means limited access to peripartum care, leading to higher risks of complications during pregnancy and childbirth [36].

The prevalence of chronic health conditions also reflects broader inequities. Obesity rates are highest among non-Hispanic Black adults (49.6%) and Hispanic adults (44.8%), compared to 42.2% for non-Hispanic white adults and just 17.4% for non-Hispanic Asian adults [37]. Asthma prevalence follows a similar trend, with Black individuals experiencing the highest asthma rates at 10.3%, White individuals at 8.4%, while Latino (6.7%) and Asian (4.4%) populations have the lowest rates [38]. Furthermore, African Americans have the highest overall cancer mortality rate of any racial or ethnic group in the U.S., illustrating the cumulative impact of structural health inequities for marginalized communities [39]. Chronic conditions like obesity and asthma are more prevalent in communities of color, increasing their likelihood of severe maternal morbidity, low birth weight, preterm birth, and small gestational growth [40].

Additionally, socioeconomic status is a critical dimension of disparity. In 2020, the poverty rate among African Americans was 19.5%, affecting 8.5 million people. Hispanic communities followed closely at 17.0% (10.4 million people), while Native Americans experienced the highest poverty rate at 23.0% (600,000 people). In contrast, the poverty rate for non-Hispanic White individuals stood at 8.2%, though they represented a larger absolute number of people living in poverty at approximately 15.9 million [41]. These socioeconomic disparities limit access to quality care, healthy environments

and food, education, and stable employment, all of which are foundational to maternal and child well-being.

Last, racial and ethnic representation within the labor force is one of the clearest examples of the unequal opportunity in the U.S. In 2023, White individuals made up 76% of the labor force, compared to 13% for Black individuals, 7% for Asians, and only 1% for AIAN individuals. NHPI accounted for just 0.5%, while those identifying as two or more races made up 2% [42]. Labor force disparities make parents in marginalized communities much less likely to be able to provide quality care and economic stability for their child, leading the entire family to have increased stress levels and poorer health outcomes [43].

These statistics provide a quantitative foundation for understanding how a lack of focus on early and preventive health equity initiatives in the U.S. causes broad social disparities to span across generations.

VII. HOW LOCAL ENVIRONMENT ALTERS HEALTH

The structural determinants of health, or a geography's cultural norms, policies, institutions, and practices, help define the MCH crisis in our country. These environmental-based factors drive inequities in access to care, health infrastructure, and ultimately, maternal and child health outcomes. Five key structural dimensions illustrate how state-level decisions and norms influence MCH equity in the United States, which include:

- **Medicaid Expansion:** States that expanded Medicaid under the ACA have reported improved access to prenatal care and reductions in maternal and infant mortality, particularly among low-income populations. States that have not expanded Medicaid continue to face higher rates of uninsured women and poorer maternal health outcomes [44].
- **Reproductive Rights:** States with restrictive reproductive health laws, often in politically conservative regions, limit access to abortion, contraception, and comprehensive reproductive care. These legal barriers are associated with elevated risks of unintended pregnancies and higher maternal mortality rates [45].
- **Public Health Funding:** States with more progressive political leadership tend to invest more in public health infrastructure, early childhood programs, and social safety nets. These investments are linked to better MCH outcomes, including reduced infant mortality and improved maternal health indicators [46].
- **Systemic Racism:** Structural racism is embedded in policies and institutional practices across the U.S., impacting access to quality care, economic stability, and psychosocial stress. These factors disproportionately affect marginalized communities and increase risks of adverse maternal outcomes [47].

- **Care Deserts:** Rural and under-resourced counties across the country often face critical shortages of obstetric providers and facilities. Long travel distances, closures of labor and delivery units due to underfunding, and lack of specialty care accelerates poor maternal health outcomes, particularly in the South and Midwest regions [47].

While this paper focuses on the crisis within the United States, it is important to recognize that maternal mortality is a global issue. Globally, especially in low income countries, maternal deaths are often attributed to the “Three Delays”: (1) delay in deciding to seek care, due to lack of awareness, stigma, or mistrust in the health system; (2) delay in reaching a health facility, often caused by poor transportation, long distances, or unsafe environments; and (3) delay in receiving quality care upon arrival, resulting from shortages of skilled providers, low cultural competence, lack of medical supplies, and weak referral systems [48].

These patterns of delay in care seen in low-resource settings can offer insight into the barriers women in the U.S. face. Though the U.S. is a high-income country, these same delays are echoed in under-resourced and underserved communities, especially among rural, low-income, and racially marginalized populations.

VIII. IMPACT OF MCH ON POPULATION HEALTH

The MCH crisis in the United States is a reflection of the country's policy failures and misplaced priorities. Despite spending more on healthcare than any other high-income country, the U.S. consistently ranks last in maternal health indicators among OECD countries [1]. This paradox is caused by the U.S. healthcare system's predominant focus being treating illness after it has already occurred, instead of investing in preventive, community-based infrastructure such as safe housing, green spaces, education, transportation, and other health interventions to stop people from getting sick in the first place. This reactive instead of proactive approach to healthcare in the U.S. results in both higher costs and worse outcomes, particularly for women of color.

More than 84% of pregnancy-related deaths in the U.S. are preventable [6], and yet the country continues to lose hundreds of lives each year due to systemic neglect and structural barriers. As health systems around the globe improve, it is unacceptable for a nation as advanced and wealthy as the U.S. to see its maternal outcomes stagnate and decline. A healthier population translates to a stronger, happier, more resilient and productive society, therefore deeply focusing on improving MCH outcomes in the U.S. is foundational for societal progress [49].

Embedded within these challenges are clear opportunities for progress. Addressing care deserts is a solvable problem through community or company based legislative

advocacy, as well as through strategic investments in the obstetric infrastructure and workforce [47]. Advocacy for policies that expand Medicaid, protect reproductive rights, and increase funding for public health services have been shown to improve MCH outcomes, as demonstrated by comparative analyses across different U.S. states [50].

Furthermore, addressing systematic racism through enforcing stricter regulations on harmful marketing practices, environmental pollutants, and spread of misinformation can mitigate many of the commonly seen upstream drivers of poor MCH [34]. Also, lobbying for equitable education, housing, and quality care in local underserved communities are essential to building environments where all birthing families can thrive. Improving maternal and child health in the U.S. is not just about saving lives, it is about affirming the value of those lives and addressing the historical and ongoing injustices that have made quality care inaccessible to many. The solutions exist, but what is needed now is the collective political and societal will to act.

IX. CONCLUSION & NEXT STEPS

This systematic literature review has examined the ongoing MCH policy crisis in the U.S. through a RCA framework, revealing that despite the nation having the highest healthcare expenditures among high-income countries, it continues to experience worsening maternal health outcomes. These outcomes are deeply rooted in systemic inequities shaped by social determinants of health, historical injustices, and power dynamics, making this a critical public health research concern.

The next phase of study is to build off this investigation to evaluate maternal health outcomes in eight U.S. states, analyzing how regionality and political climate (Republican vs. Democratic governance) both influence such outcomes. The four most populous democratic and republican states will be selected, and "Republican" or "Democratic" governance classification will be defined as the party in power of our country (U.S. president) during a decade-long study period (2015 - 2025). This evaluation of power dynamics will be based upon public data sources such as the Center for Disease Control and Prevention, National Institutes of Health, World Health Organization, state health departments, and other resources focusing on metrics such as maternal mortality rates, NSTV rates, infant mortality, and additional variables relevant to the social determinants of health, access to prenatal and postnatal care, as well as access to insurance coverage and other resources. To guarantee impartiality, the study will use peer-reviewed literature and secondary data to ensure a data-driven analysis, rather than providing politically biased viewpoints.

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